

-

Name of Interviewer	DMU 1
Partner	DMU
Date of Interview	13 th June 2019
Duration of interview audio recording	36mins 38secs
Stakeholder type	NPO
Country	N/A - Network
Anonymity	Did they wave anonymity to be case study: NO

I: Interviewer

R: Respondent

R: Hello?

I: Hi, Finally!

R: Hello. We had two meetings and I thought you were in my invited meeting so we have been crossing here, but anyhow.

I: Right, so, first of all, please can you tell me about your position and your tasks in the [XXXX] network?

R: Okay. So I am the official correspondent, the contact person from my home organisation. My organisation is [XXXXX]. It's one of the [XXXX] members. It is an official network in the sense that it's a legal entity and it's composed of member organisations. I am the Chief Contact Person from my organisation towards [XXXXXX]. I have been doing that since 2007, so 12 years.

I: How did you join the network?

R: Well, [XXXXX], my organisation, was one of the founding members of [XXXXX] back in 2005 perhaps or so. I don't remember exactly. Anyhow, we are one of the founding members, (unclear 00:02:34).

I: Over time has your role changed within the network?

R: My role perhaps in the sense that I have become more and more one of the core members from the strategy point of view, so I am really, let's say, if I may say so from the inner circle. So my role has strengthened over time, of course, yes.

I: Do you know all the other members of your network?

R: Well, I know the key members. We have I think more than 350 member organisations. You can't know them all. But I know my peers as strategy managers, in the biggest member organisations, the biggest RTOs, and maybe 11 RTOs who are the absolute core in terms of critical mass. I know

my contact persons well in that group and of course the secretariat who runs the office. I know them.

I: How often do you meet?

R: Face to face perhaps, it depends, maybe once or even twice a month, but there is regular correspondence through email. They are part of my closest colleagues, the people in the [XXXXX] core group, so through email almost daily, maybe face to face once or twice a month.

I: Do you think personal ties play a big role within the network?

R: Absolutely. Yes.

I: Do you think it's important to know each other to build trust?

R: Yes it is.

I: Could you explain a bit more why you think that is the case?

R: Well, as I explained, we have defined issues of common joint interest and [XXXX] is, of course, an interest organisation in the sense that we are driving the interests of European RTOs in Brussels together. To do so, we really need to have common understanding of what we are doing and what our goals are and it takes frequent dialogue and it is so much more easy if you know the people, of course; you can call anytime you need to and you don't need to pretend something, it's really like between close colleagues, so personal links and trust is the key.

I: Can you give us a historical perspective of the network? Here we are looking at the context of the emergence of the network. When and why was the network launched and has it been changing over time?

R: The reason it was launched was that the founding members back in 2005, if it was that year, they had been meeting each other for a longer time, mainly the management of some organisations and sharing their experiences and best practices and identifying the (unclear 00:07:10) that the RTOs are quite similar. The big RTOs, we have a similar role in our national innovation systems. We share a lot of common issues and we can learn from each other and we can support each other and we can support each other by joining forces and working for our interests in the European landscape. So that's the historical background, and it's still the same, whether environment, whether so-called business environment, if you may say so. It's changing all the time. We need to adapt ourselves all the time and doing it together we can really have a stronger influence on how the environment is developing. So more or less the need for this collaboration and the need for this network has remained unchanged.

I: What do you do as network members to achieve your goals? So here I am asking about, I am looking for the activities that you do within [XXXX].

R: Within [XXXXX], we do policy influencing, or let's say influencing as policy on framework level, and we collaborate very strongly with European institutions

and the focus is really on commissions, but we do have links to all institutions. What was your question?

I: It was just about are there any specific activities that you do within [XXXX] towards..?

R: So specific activities, they deal with the let's say European policies and programmes for research and innovation, mainly framework programmes but more and more other programmes like structural funds or some other initiatives like industrial policy, and we want to be part of this kind of discussion. Then there is like funding roles or participation (unclear 00:10:00) or priorities of this (unclear 00:10:05) long programmes. Then there are issues which are more thematic content-wise and these issues are taken care of by our research networks. We are active in all imaginable technology areas and there are professional networks, and they do project-level activities in those networks but [XXXXX] takes care of the framework conditions in the long run. So this is the division of work really.

I: I would like to move now to the structure and format of your network. Could you describe to me the structure of [XXXXX]? I am meaning the structure in terms of are there any chapters? Are there sub-networks or divisions? What's the legal character for [XXXX]? Is it a company? Is it an association? How do you formulate activities?

R: [XXXX] has a governance mechanism. We have a secretary-general with a very small secretariat of professional staff. They are governed by [XXXX] board. [XXXX] board is composed of – it's a rotational thing, a member organisations in [XXXX] and the board members – I don't remember how many, maybe 10 or 15, they are selected for a certain period and we rotate the membership in the board. Then there is a steering board which is the more preparatory level, very strategic level. That is mostly composed of the bigger member organisations. That is the governance of [XXXX]. Then the secretariat is facilitating the work of some selected working groups that are active and working groups are open, any member organisation may join a working group. We have working groups like a working group for FPs, that means Framework Programmes, one working group for structural funds, one for legal affairs, one for financial issues.

These are the so-called policy level working groups. Then there are some thematic working groups, one on space, one on data, and one on security and defence. This is how we operate. It's a legal structure and permanent structure. It has been there since 2005. It is like a company in that sense but it is not a company, it's an interest association.

I: Can you tell me who decided to choose this structure about [XXXX]?

R: The founding members back in history.

I: Is the network based on any other networks that were there previously or is it something that was completely designed for [XXXX]?

R: I think there must have been some networks but this became more institutional, so that's how it went.

I: Do you think there are any pros or cons for this specific network model based on your experience?

R: No. It's very straightforward and clear.

I: So there are not any issues regarding membership, regarding funding, regarding the geographic spread of the network?

R: The funding comes through a membership piece. There are different fee categories depending on the size of the member. The bigger organisations like (unclear 00:15:20) pay a bigger membership fee than the smallest one. The geographical spread is as good as it can be. For example, in the EU13 member states, we hardly have any RTOs, so that is the main reason we don't have many members from EU13 because they don't have these kinds of organisations. Many of EU13 countries are in a state of building up some RTO type of organisations. So maybe with time, the geographical spread will be more dense.

I: Under responsible research and innovation, one of the themes I talked about most is diversity and gender. For [XXXX], would you say diversity and gender plays a big role?

R: It's not an issue for [XXXXX], gender issue, no. It's not an issue for us.

I: What sort of mechanisms are there in place to address these issues? Let's say gender or diversity. How do you make it?

R: We don't address these issues.

I: Why don't you address them?

R: This is totally out of scope. A very strange question.

I: I will move on then from this question. Now we are going to talk about the membership model. So regarding your membership model, can you describe it in detail? So what is the range of membership options?

R: Membership options, I don't remember, maybe there are one or two or three categories, depending on the size of the organisation and the member organisation and the turnover, the budget or whatever you call it. There are categories in terms of the membership fee. It's just the membership fee category; the whole activity of [XXXX] is open for anybody who wants to contribute, so there are no restrictions. So I can't explain it better. It's on a voluntary basis how you contribute. Then the information is shared and that's how it works.

I: Okay, so do you look at individual members or do you look at members associated to a specific organisation, for example? For example, if I wanted to be a member, would I join as an individual member or do I have to join as part of an organisation?

R: No personal members. I am not a member, my organisation is a member. There are no individual members. So it's always an organisation who is a member.

I: For members what sort of rights or tasks do they have? So here I am looking at say for example voting rights or decision-making rights? Are these open to the network members?

R: Yes, it is. The voting rights are – it's equal in the general assembly, which is meeting once a year, and then the board is represented by the members, so it's in the statute, and I am not able to explain the statute. It's everything is there but it's very inclusive.

I: In your opinion, why do you think members join the network? Are there any incentives for being a member?

R: Members join because they understand that by being part of [XXXX] they can access very good knowledge and information and they can access excellent networks by being part. They can be part of an RTO community which is active in the European research and innovation collaboration. So members can have a positive impact on their own activities through being a member of [XXXX].

I: Now I am going to move on to the networking funding model. Here I am going to touch on governance and/or management of the network and also I will touch on the funding sources that you employ at [XXXX]. So can you tell me which sources you utilise for funding?

R: For funding, it is just the membership fee. [XXXX] is not doing any European projects, for example.

I: Do you know if [XXXX] has an annual budget?

R: Yes. The annual budget is there, and it covers the wages of the secretariat, more or less, and normal running costs of the secretary and the (ph 00:21:51) *events* of the office and all that type of activities, the running costs.

I: Do you have any longer-term budget projections?

R: Yes, we have to because this is a serious employer for these people. So this is not a project. This is an association with a solid mechanism for making such that people get their salaries and we can run the business.

I: Now I will move on to governance. So can you tell me in detail again who has the managing responsibilities in the network? So here I want to understand if there are a board of directors or executive committee, advisory board, etc?

R: No, no executive committees, no nothing. We have the president of [XXXX] and vice president and they are representing the larger community. They are the face of [XXXX] and they are selected for three years in a row and the secretary-general is like the CEO and the board is the board. So this is how it works. There is nothing like in some PPPs they have this executive committee etc. We have a lean structure. This is like a company in that sense.

I: What sort of expertise do you look for, for people to be on the management board or the management structure for [XXXX]?

R: It needs to be the CEO Director-General of the respective member organisation, or someone very close to the top management.

I: Regarding communication, is there any regular communication? Do you have regular management meetings? If so, how frequent do you have them?

R: The board and the steering board meet regularly, several times a year. Then there are meetings for the wider membership of [XXXX], we have an annual meeting and then we have annual events in Brussels, so we have a regular sort of setup of activities which are repeated on an annual basis.

I: What do you discuss at the annual meetings for all the members?

R: You can compare it like an annual meeting, a general assembly meeting. It's like if you own some stocks of a company and you go to the owners meeting, it's similar, it's normal let's say management stuff and yearly report stuff and budget stuff and things like that are the main highlights of the work of the previous year. So that's what we discuss in the meetings. Then there is the annual meeting, the programme part is more, it's open for anybody who wants to come and we invite commission officials and high-rank administrative people from our member states and industry to attend these meetings. It's like a seminar or a workshop.

I: Do you have a five-year road map or something like a gun chart that is publicly available?

R: Yes, if you Google [XXXX] you can find our reports and precision papers on the net.

I: Moving on, do you have a risk and mitigation plan? Do you foresee any risks that might affect the effectiveness of [XXXX]?

R: We have a mitigation plan so that there is a pot of money, a surplus, collected, in case something dramatic happens that we need to close for some strange reason we need to close the [XXXX] activities. The people who are employed will be secured in salary for so many months. So that's the mitigation plan. This is not a project. This is different things. So (unclear 00:28:00) is out of scope in our case, again like the gender issue.

I: Can you describe to me how information is made available and circulated among [XXXX] members?

R: You can always go and talk with the Secretary-General. You can join any of our programmes. You can read the internal [XXXX] members website. It is as open as it can be.

I: What would you say are the general issues that affect the effectiveness of the governance of the [XXXX] network? For instance, trust issues?

R: Oh yes. That's normal human being. It's based on human relationships and that's why we organise quite a few meetings and events on a yearly basis to facilitate the development and maintenance of our relations on a personal level. It's all about people, of course.

I: Okay, thanks. Now I will move on to challenges and problems within the network. So what sort of problems does the [XXXX] network face?

R: It's always a continuity challenge when people come and go. So it's a continuous the need to make sure that the relationships are postured. So I don't see any other... Then of course challenges are sometimes such that if there is some restructuring or something going on in one organisation they may not be able to contribute to the common (unclear 00:30:28) as much as needed but this is a normal phenomenon. So I can't give a better answer.

I: That's good enough. One of the issues for networks like [XXXX] could face is the cultural differences considering that its members come from a number of countries. How do you deal with these cultural differences?

R: This is a strange question for me. Of course, we come from different countries. We all speak English. Those people who are not able to adjust to intercultural collaboration, they will never become strong members of the network, it's as simple as that. I never really notice any difficulties in working with different cultures. It's perhaps not relevant in our case, as a question.

I: The last question is as you understand the RRING project is trying to establish a network, so what could you warn us about any potential pitfalls that may be if we wanted to establish our own network? So what sort of things should we be aware of when we want to establish our own network? Hello? Hello?

(Line goes dead 00:32:38-00:32:47)

I: Hello. Can you hear me?

R: Yes. It was switched off for a while.

I: My last question, one of the things that we want to do in the RRING project is to establish our own network. So from your own experience, what sort of things would you warn us in terms of establishing a network? Are there any pitfalls that we need to be aware of or any risks that we should be aware of?

R: If you are establishing a network, it's different from establishing a legal entity. Are you intending to establish a legal entity?

I: At this moment in time, we are not sure about the nature of the network, so that's why we...

R: Don't go for a legal entity. You need lawyers there and then you can be sure that it's getting really difficult. You need to agree on this and that and it takes lots of effort and lots of different professional skills. If it's a network, I don't know. A network is growing by itself. If it's a project, it's different from establishing a network. You need to work on it on your own. There are so many ways to do a collaboration.

I: For example, can you give me an example of a way of doing it other than following the legal route?

R: Doing like a club (laughs). Maybe you need to organise something on a yearly basis, organise something which goes on and gives you continuity, the places for dialogue and meeting people and ways to co-publish things and these kinds of elements, but really don't start with a legal structure because then it becomes so complicated.

I: **Okay. That's it. We have gone through all of the questions. Thank you very much for sharing your experience.**

R: Thank you.

I: **In particular, for taking the time for this interview.**

R: I hope you got something. I don't have any questions. You really do want me to sign the consent paper, is it so important for you? I don't know when I'm next time in the office and the next job for me to do it, but I will do it if you need it.

I: **Yes. We will definitely need it.**

R: Okay, then I will do it.

I: **Thank you very much for your time. I know some of the questions were not relevant for you but you tried to answer the questions as much as you could. We appreciate that.**

R: Thank you. Take care. Bye.

I: **Bye.**

(End of recording)